

Safety in the Game Meat Chain

2nd General Meeting

09–10 June 2026, Bucharest

Abstracts

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Preface

Dear colleagues and friends,

It is my pleasure to welcome you to the 2nd General Meeting of the SafeGameMeat COST Action. This abstract book reflects the scientific diversity, collaborative spirit and shared commitment of our network to improving safety along the game meat chain.

The contributions collected here address a wide range of topics, including biological hazards, zoonotic parasites, wildlife diseases, antimicrobial resistance, hygiene, chemical contaminants, radionuclides, legislation, traceability, training, and consumer perception. Together, they demonstrate how closely game meat safety is linked to animal health, public health, environmental conditions and responsible use of natural resources.

Game meat is an important food resource with strong cultural, ecological and economic dimensions. Ensuring its safety requires cooperation across disciplines, sectors and countries. This is precisely the aim of SafeGameMeat: to connect expertise, exchange knowledge and support a transnational One Health approach to current and emerging challenges in the game meat chain.

I would like to thank all authors, Working Group members, organisers and participants for their valuable contributions and continued engagement. I hope that this General Meeting will stimulate fruitful discussions, strengthen existing collaborations and inspire new ideas for the future work of our Action.

Dr Anneluise Mader, Action Chair
and the Scientific Committee of the conference

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1 Abstracts – Oral Presentations

1.1 Hunting and Processing

1.1.1 The hunting sector and game meat chain in Bosnia and Herzegovina: current state and challenges

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Research publications regarding the hunting sector and the game meat chain in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BaH) are visibly scarce. In 2024, there were a total of 62,000 registered hunters within the hunting sectors of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FBH) and the Republika Srpska (RS), covering hunting grounds of 4,455,000 hectares. This lack of data motivated us to conduct an on-site screening investigation as a Short Scientific Mission within the framework of the COST Action “SafeGameMeat,” focusing on hunting organisations, the game meat market, and by-product disposal. Currently, there are no official statistics for the hunting bag for the entirety of BaH, compounded by the absence of registered game-handling establishments in the country. An exception is data from the Hunting Association of RS, which reported that 1,331 kg of roe deer meat and 5,095 kg of wild boar meat were processed in 2024. Facilitated by the Association of Hunting Organisations in BaH, personal surveys and visits were conducted across 13 municipal hunting societies: Olovo, Vogošća, Kiseljak, Visoko, Zenica, Kakanj, Sanski Most, Bihać, Zavidovići, Maglaj, Doboju-Jug, and Tešanj. Interestingly, in the FBH, 90% of the surveyed hunting associations own cold storage facilities for game meat and small areas for primary processing. Nearly all (99%) interviewed hunters stated that they do not sell the meat; instead, they consume it themselves or distribute it to other hunters. This is particularly true for wild boar meat, which Bosniak (Muslim) hunters do not consume. Regarding compliance with European Union legislation, there is significant room for improvement, especially in capacity building for all stakeholders in the “forest-to-fork” chain: hunters, veterinary practitioners, state veterinary officers, and consumers.

1.1.2 Large game meat supply chains outside EU hygiene regulations: a pilot study on hunters' practices

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The management of large wild game meat that falls outside the scope of EU food legislation remains a complex regulatory challenge, raising concerns about legal interpretation, controls, traceability, and food safety risks. This pilot study investigates the practical implementation of existing provisions, focusing on carcasses handled outside Game Handling Establishments (GHEs), within a broader project examining these aspects from the Competent Authority perspective.

A structured questionnaire was administered to 48 hunters to collect data on carcass handling, processing, transport, and traceability. Respondents were exclusively male (100%), mainly from Southern Italy. Wild boar was the most commonly hunted species, reported as the sole target species by 56.2% of respondents and in combination with roe deer by 29.2%.

Evisceration was performed within three hours post-harvest in 79.2% of cases. Transport was mainly carried out using non-refrigerated vehicles (68.8%) or containers (25.0%), whereas refrigerated systems were used in only 4.2% of cases.

Processing locations varied considerably according to the intended destination of the meat. For self-consumption, 52.1% of carcasses were processed in private dwellings, 41.7% in collection centres, and 6.2% exclusively through the GHE pathway. For direct consumer supply, 45.8% were processed privately, 37.5% in collection centres, and 12.5% in GHEs. For retail distribution, 31.2% were processed in collection centres, 29.2% privately, and only 14.6% in GHEs. Overall, more than 50% of carcasses were handled in non-regulated settings.

Traceability systems were consistently applied in 68.8% of cases. Post-mortem inspection/examination was performed by trained hunters (67.7%) or veterinarians (25.8% official, 6.5% freelance). These findings reveal persistent gaps between regulatory requirements and field practices, particularly regarding the limited integration of GHEs into the hunted game meat supply chain.

1.1.3 Communal hunting and zoonotic risk in northern Ghana: A One Health perspective

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Communal hunting is a longstanding cultural practice among several ethnic groups in northern Ghana, particularly the Dagomba, and is most commonly undertaken during the late dry season (March–April). Communal hunts involve predominantly young men (often 300–500 per group) who mobilize from towns and cities and travel long distances into the hinterland using trucks and motorbikes. Hunting is conducted collectively, with large groups moving through landscapes to flush wildlife from refugia, thereby increasing harvest efficiency. Commonly captured species include *Lepus capensis*, *Numida meleagris*, *Kobus kob kob*, *Thryonomys swinderianus*, and various rodent taxa. Game is captured using firearms, locally fabricated clubs (e.g., Kpahi), and hunting dogs, which may serve as potential bridging hosts for pathogen transmission between wildlife and humans. Post-harvest handling practices constitute critical points of zoonotic exposure, particularly to infections such as Lassa fever, Ebola virus disease, Leptospirosis, and Monkeypox. Carcasses are frequently transported on the backs of hunters or in sacks, often without protective barriers, increasing the likelihood of direct contact with blood, bodily fluids, and ectoparasites. In many instances, preliminary processing (e.g., evisceration and butchering) occurs under field conditions with limited hygiene, further elevating risks of exposure to pathogens such as viruses, bacteria, and parasites associated with wild mammals. Additionally, the aggregation of hunters and shared handling of carcasses may facilitate intra-community transmission pathways. These findings highlight the need for culturally sensitive risk mitigation strategies, including targeted health education for over 90% of hunters and the promotion of safer handling practices as part of One Health interventions. Recognizing the socio-cultural and economic significance of communal hunting, the paper advocates for balanced approaches that safeguard both public health and traditional livelihoods.

Key words: game meat, zoonotic diseases, practices, West Africa

1.2 Chemical Hazards

1.2.1 Landscape- and diet-related patterns of trace element accumulation in wild boar livers from Brandenburg, Germany: a preliminary study

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The aim of our study was to characterize trace element concentrations in wild boar liver and to explore whether among-individual variation is associated with biological traits, isotope-based dietary indicators and landscape characteristics. Wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) is closely linked to local habitats through its foraging behaviour, and has been proposed as a sentinel species for environmental contamination with trace elements. It is also a widely hunted game species in Europe, making tissue contamination relevant from both environmental and food-safety perspectives. This preliminary study examined liver samples from 82 wild boars collected in 12 hunting districts in Brandenburg, Germany. The characteristics of the districts varied in land-use composition, expressed as the proportions of urban, industrial, agricultural and forested areas.

Liver samples were analysed for 20 trace elements, including As, Cd, Hg and Pb, using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) after microwave-assisted nitric acid digestion. The liver was selected because many trace elements are stored, metabolized or detoxified in this organ, making it particularly relevant for assessing exposure in wildlife. Stable carbon and nitrogen isotope ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) were determined by isotope ratio mass spectrometry to provide complementary indicators of assimilated diet and habitat-related foraging patterns. Age class and sex were included as individual-level variables.

Element-specific associations with age, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, landscape context and hunting district indicate distinct exposure pathways for As, Cd, Hg and Pb. By integrating elemental analysis, stable isotope data and spatial information, the study provides a framework for assessing wildlife exposure to trace elements and for evaluating the potential role of wild boar in environmental and food-safety monitoring.

1.2.2 Lead Contamination in Game Meat: A Systematic Review of Ammunition-Derived Exposure

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Lead exposure through the consumption of wild game meat has emerged as a relevant food safety concern. Unlike meat from farmed animals, game meat may contain residues of lead originating from hunting ammunition, as bullet and gunshot fragmentation can disperse particles into edible tissues. Given the well-documented toxic effects of lead, lead dietary exposure from this source is of concern, particularly for vulnerable groups.

The present study provides a literature review aimed at integrating current knowledge on ammunition-derived lead contamination in hunted game meat. A systematic search was conducted in major scientific databases using predefined strings. A total of 1,828 records were initially identified, and after screening and eligibility assessment, 45 studies were included. A descriptive synthesis of the selected studies was performed.

Overall, the reviewed studies report highly variable but frequently elevated lead concentrations across species. The most frequently investigated wild hunted species included woodcock, pheasant, red deer and wild boar. The highest levels are frequently observed in small game birds, but also in large game species extreme lead values are reported. Notably, about 80% of the mean concentrations reported across some of these studies exceeded the reference value of 0.1 mg/kg, thus exceeding the European regulatory limits set for meat from farmed livestock.

Despite variability in analytical approaches and study designs, the evidence consistently highlights the presence of lead residues in edible tissues of hunted animals. This confirms that ammunition-derived lead contamination represents a relevant and still under-regulated food safety issue. Further harmonisation of analytical methods and consideration of strategies to reduce lead exposure, including alternative ammunition, may help prevent potential risks for consumers.

1.2.3 Barriers and Opportunities in the Transition to Lead-Free Ammunition: Evidence from Italian Hunters

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The study examines the use of lead ammunition in hunting, focusing on Italian hunters' perceptions of both lead and non-toxic alternatives. Despite strong scientific evidence on environmental and human health risks, along with increasingly stringent EU regulations, lead ammunition remains the preferred choice among European hunters. Although technical alternatives are available, evidence from other countries shows that their adoption is hindered by higher costs, doubts about performance, concerns over firearm compatibility, and a strong cultural attachment to traditional practices. To assess whether a similar situation applies in Italy, this study investigates perceptions, knowledge, and barriers through an online survey (582 responses) conducted in summer 2025.

The results indicate a generally low perception of the risks associated with lead ammunition, varying by hunting type: big game hunters show greater concern than small game hunters, who are also the most resistant to change. Overall, concern levels remain modest. Notably, the primary concern relates to potential reputational damage to hunting rather than to health or environmental impacts. Well-documented risks—such as the consumption of contaminated meat, neurological harm, and dog poisoning—appear to be widely underestimated.

Lead is perceived as superior in terms of effectiveness, accuracy, safety, and availability, while alternatives are considered weaker in these aspects but more advantageous in terms of regulatory compliance. Price and environmental impact play only a limited role in decision-making.

In summary, the transition of the Italian hunting community to lead-free ammunition is hindered by a mismatch between regulatory advantages and perceived technical performance. Promoting change requires targeted risk communication, practical training, economic incentives, and the involvement of hunting associations to transform regulatory pressure into a shared and informed choice.

1.2.4 Hidden Contaminants in Wild Boars: Caesium-137 in Meat and Strontium-90 in Bones

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The persistence of long-lived radionuclides in terrestrial ecosystems remains a significant challenge for food safety, particularly in the context of game meat consumption. Wild boars (*Sus scrofa*), due to their foraging behaviour and interaction with contaminated soil layers, are especially prone to radionuclide accumulation and may represent a relevant source of dietary exposure.

This study investigates the occurrence of Cs-137 in wild boar muscle tissue and Sr-90 in bones. A total of 147 individuals were analysed. Activity concentrations of Cs-137 in meat were determined using gamma spectrometry, while Sr-90 in bones was measured following radiochemical separation and beta counting. Samples collected in 2024–2025 included muscle tissues (n = 137) and bone samples (n = 10) from wild boars inhabiting Poland.

The results confirm the presence of Cs-137 in edible tissues, with activity concentrations ranging from 0.39 to 272.2 Bq/kg. In the past two years, measured concentrations have not approached the maximum permitted levels specified in European Union regulations (e.g., Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No. 2020/1158 and related acts). However, over the past decade, values exceeding 600 Bq/kg have been recorded, raising concerns about long-term consumer protection. Given the increasing consumption of game meat, these findings indicate that wild boar meat may represent an under-recognised pathway of radionuclide intake.

Although Sr-90 is not directly associated with edible tissues, its presence in bones (0.13–7.36 Bq/kg) reflects long-term environmental contamination and ongoing transfer processes within ecosystems. This suggests that current monitoring strategies, which primarily focus on muscle tissue, may not fully capture radionuclide persistence and bioavailability in the food chain.

Enhanced surveillance of wild boar meat, particularly in areas with a known history of contamination, should be considered essential to ensure consumer safety and support evidence-based regulatory decision-making.

1.2.5 Human exposure to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) via consumption of meat and offal from game animals in Germany

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Game meat is a popular and sustainable alternative to conventional meats, with Germans consuming nearly 25,500 tons of wild ungulate meat in the 2022/2023 hunting year. However, consumers are largely unaware of significant risks, particularly exposure to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS).

PFAS are pervasive environmental contaminants found in soil and water, which wild animals ingest through their diet. These substances accumulate in the food chain, and game meat and offal are substantial contributors to human dietary PFAS intake, especially for groups like hunters' families. High PFAS levels are linked to adverse health effects, including reduced birth weight, impaired antibody response, elevated cholesterol, and liver damage. Four key PFAS (PFHxS, PFOS, PFOA, PFNA) are of particular concern, with a Tolerable Weekly Intake (TWI) set by EFSA to mitigate health risks. Game animals serve as a crucial link between environmental pollution and human exposure. Monitoring them not only protects consumers but also provides insights into environmental contamination.

This work focuses on roe deer and wild boar, examining PFAS occurrence, analytical methods, influencing factors, and the associated consumer risks in Germany.

1.3 Trade Network and Supply Chain

1.3.1 Bridging the Gap: Integrating One Health and the Ecosystem Approach within the Global Biodiversity Framework for Safe Game Meat Systems

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The growing recognition of zoonotic risks, environmental change, and biodiversity loss has reinforced the need for integrated frameworks linking human, animal, and ecosystem health. The One Health concept (that the health of people, animals, and the environment are interconnected) has become central to addressing food safety challenges, including those associated with wild game meat; however, its application often remains focused on pathogens, with insufficient consideration of broader ecological dynamics.

This presentation highlights the need to combine One Health with the Ecosystem Approach, which promotes integrated management of land, water, and living resources. In game meat systems, this combined framework enables a more comprehensive understanding of how hunting practices, wildlife population dynamics, habitat integrity, and environmental contaminants interact to shape food safety outcomes.

This integration is increasingly reflected in global policy. Under the 2022 Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Parties committed to ensuring that the use and trade of wild species are sustainable, safe, and legal. The CBD’s Global Action Plan on Biodiversity and Health further emphasizes ecosystem integrity as a prerequisite for preventing disease emergence and ensuring food safety.

At the international level, the Quadripartite (CBD, WHO, FAO, WOA) One Health Joint Plan of Action (2022–2026) promotes cross-sectoral approaches linking biodiversity, sustainable use, and human health, while assessments by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) highlight how ecosystem degradation increases disease risks and undermines food system safety.

Integrating the Ecosystem Approach with the One Health concept adds an essential ecological perspective, ensuring that game meat safety is addressed across the entire system, from wildlife populations and habitats to consumption, offering a pathway toward more resilient, sustainable, and safe game meat systems.

1.3.2 Fragmented Systems, Shared Risks: A One Health Analysis of Expert Perspectives on South Africa's Game Meat Sector

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There is growing interest in formalising a safe and sustainable game meat sector, particularly in Southern Africa. While widely consumed, its expansion remains contested due to concerns around zoonotic disease risk and environmental sustainability. South Africa hosts one of the most developed commercial wildlife ranching industries globally, occupying 14–17% of the country's land area, where game meat production is receiving renewed policy attention. National targets aim to double production by 2036, yet zoonotic disease risks continue to threaten this trajectory through trade restrictions, regulatory uncertainty, and environmental pressures.

This study applies a One Health framework to examine how animal health, food safety systems, and environmental management intersect within the sector. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 19 experts across wildlife veterinary practice, meat inspection, conservation science, and policy. Findings indicate that risks are shaped less by pathogen presence alone than by how regulatory structures, market pathways, and production intensity influence oversight and management. Trade-linked diseases such as Foot-and-Mouth Disease primarily affect animal movement and market access, while food safety compliance varies between export-oriented and domestic systems. Environmental outcomes are similarly influenced by production intensity and land-use practices.

Under projected sectoral expansion, regulatory fragmentation, uneven market formalisation, and intensification may amplify risks across animal, human, and environmental health. Despite clear interconnections, governance remains siloed, limiting coordinated responses. The study highlights the need to operationalise One Health approaches within game meat governance to strengthen alignment between regulatory systems and production realities, supporting integrated surveillance and management.

1.3.3 Trends in meat consumption, and consumer attitudes and preferences towards game meat in the Czech Republic

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The Czech Republic has a long-standing tradition of hunting, and consuming game meat. Contemporary consumer perceptions often reflect historical associations of game meat with noble cuisine and special or festive occasions. Changes in landscape structure driven by human activities and shifts in agricultural production have influenced both the composition and abundance of hunted game species. At present, the country is facing overpopulation of wild boar and several species of deer, which has led to increased availability and supply of game meat on the market. Although per capita consumption of game meat remains relatively low (1.2 kg in 2024, according to the Czech Statistical Office), it has tripled compared with levels observed two decades ago. The aim of this study was to evaluate Czech consumers' attitudes and preferences towards game meat, to identify changes in these preferences between 2017 and 2025, and to analyse differences in consumption patterns and preferences across selected sociodemographic groups. The results indicate that, for the majority of the population, game meat is still consumed only occasionally, while approximately 12% of respondents report weekly consumption. Throughout the observed period, wild boar meat remained the most preferred type of game meat and simultaneously accounted for the largest share of total harvested game. Game meat is particularly valued for its low-fat content and its perception as an ethically produced food. However, a distinct segment of the population, especially younger consumers and women living in urban areas, tends to avoid game meat consumption. These findings highlight both the growing potential and the persistent barriers associated with game meat consumption in the Czech consumer market. Funding from project METROFOOD-CZ (MEYS No: LM2023064) is acknowledged.

1.4 Biological Hazards

1.4.1 Vector-borne parasitic diseases emerged in Fenno-Scandinavian cervids; a threat to Arctic food safety and security

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The nematodes *Setaria tundra*, *Onchocerca* spp. and *Rumenfilaria andersoni* appear to have emerged in Fenno-Scandinavian reindeer during the latter half of the 20th century, associated with microfilaremia, peritonitis, necrotic granulomas and tarsitis. Geographic shifts linked to climate warming and host colonization to reindeer from sources in white-tailed deer, roe deer and red deer have served as precursors and drivers of these parasites and associated diseases. Thousands of reindeer died in 1973 during emergence of *S. tundra* followed by recurrent outbreaks in 1989 among moose and in 2003–06 and 2014 among reindeer leading to condemnation of carcasses during reindeer slaughter. Concurrently, chronic tarsitis and necrotic granulomas in liver and muscles, caused by *Onchocerca* spp., were increasingly common in reindeer and moose. In 2004–06, previously unrecognized parasites were found in the lymphatic vessels of reindeer, and were identified, for the first time in Europe, as *Rumenfilaria andersoni*. In Finnish semi-domesticated reindeer, prevalence of *R. andersoni* was locally up to 95%. In moose, the observed prevalence was 10%, in wild forest reindeer 69%, white-tailed deer 15% and roe deer 3%. Our current data, suggest this filarioid became established in Finland recently with introduction of white-tailed deer from North America in 1935. Mosquitoes transmit *S. tundra* and black flies *Onchocerca* spp., whereas the vector of *R. andersoni* is unknown. We demonstrated that high mean summer temperatures exceeding 14 °C drive the emergence of disease outbreaks due to *S. tundra*, where morbidity manifests in the following summer, if conditions remain warm. This hypothesis was further supported in autumn of 2014 following 2 consecutive exceptionally warm summers, leading to the emergence of the most recent outbreaks of *S. tundra* and *Onchocerca*. Since then, there have been yearly outbreaks. Although not zoonotic through meat consumption, filarioids can cause significant morbidity, affecting the appearance, texture and quality of meat and organs, as well as impacting body condition, and causing mortality. The consequent meat condemnation, and possible population level impacts (declines), have broader impacts on food security for northern people who depend on reindeer for food and income.

1.4.2 Regulatory and Practical Variability in *Trichinella* Testing of Wild Boar Meat intended for Private Consumption in Europe

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Private consumption of wild boar meat is increasingly widespread across Europe. Testing wild boar meat for *Trichinella* sp. is mandatory when the meat is placed on the market. However, when the meat is intended for private consumption, taking the test is optional. A cross-sectional survey was conducted on *Trichinella* sp. detection in wild boar meat intended for private consumption in 26 European countries, within the framework of the COST Action SafeGameMeat (CA22166) Working Group 4. This presentation focuses on i) data collection on the number of wild boars intended for private consumption, ii) prevalence of *Trichinella* spp. in wild boars; and iii) *Trichinella* testing. Out of 26 countries, only 6 (23.1%) reported data about the number of wild boars intended for private consumption at national level. The number of wild boars ranged from 187,516 in Poland to 11,108 in Bulgaria, highlighting the high amount of wild boar meat intended for private consumption in these countries. *Trichinella* sp. testing is not mandatory for self-consumed wild boar meat in 12 investigated countries, representing a potential risk gap for consumers. Out of these 12 countries, only five reported the *Trichinella* sp. prevalence (range from 0.1% in Poland and Romania to 6.1% in Bulgaria) in wild boars intended for private consumption. The artificial digestion method is the standard procedure used in all countries, but trichinoscopy is still in use in some countries. For the first time, this study provides information on *Trichinella* sp. detection in wild boar meat intended for private consumption in Europe. The results highlight a substantial heterogeneity in national regulations and notification system, raising public health concerns due to the risk of *Trichinella* spp. infection.

1.4.3 High seroprevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in wild boars hunted for human consumption in Italy

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Toxoplasma gondii (Apicomplexa, Sarcocystidae) is a ubiquitous zoonotic protozoan, causing toxoplasmosis, one of the most common parasitic zoonoses worldwide. The rise of hunted wild boars with an increased consumption of their meat is considered an emerging risk factor for the transmission of food-borne pathogens, including *T. gondii* infection in humans. This study aims to assess the seroprevalence of *T. gondii* in wild boars hunted for human consumption in Italy.

From April to November 2024, blood samples were collected from 96 wild boars regularly hunted within the regional wildlife surveillance program and destined for human consumption in the Lombardy region. For each animal, individual data (age and sex), sampling date, and hunting municipality were collected. Serum samples were analyzed for *T. gondii* using an indirect immunofluorescence antibody test (IFAT) using an initial screening dilution of 1:50 and FITC anti-pig IgG as conjugate (Megacor, Austria). Overall, 96 wild boars, 55 males and 11 females, hunted from 12 municipalities, were included in the study; these animals belonged to three age classes: young (n = 12), subadults (n = 22), and adults (n = 21).

37 animals tested positive for *T. gondii* specific antibodies (P = 38.5%, 95% CI: 28.8–48.3). A higher prevalence of parasite infection was detected in males than in females (26/55, P = 47.3% and 11/41, P = 26.8%, respectively), with male ones being more likely to test seropositive (OR = 2.4, p = 0.047). Seropositivity to *T. gondii* was higher in adults (12/21, P = 57.1%) than in young and subadults animals (5/12, P = 41.7% and 9/22, P = 40.9%). The seroprevalence was higher in animals hunted in autumn (15/35, P = 42.3%) than in the spring-summer season (22/61, P = 36.1%).

These findings highlight the role of wild boars in maintaining the wild cycle of *T. gondii* in a highly anthropized area, representing a bioindicator of the environmental contamination and the risk of transmission to domestic hosts.

1.4.4 *Staphylococcus aureus* at the wildlife–livestock interface: Occurrence and genomic insights from Northern German game species

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Game species play a key role in the maintenance and transmission of infectious agents at the wildlife–livestock interface and represent an important source of food for humans. Increasing overlap between wildlife habitats and livestock systems raises questions about pathogen exchange, particularly under more extensive production conditions. In addition, the occurrence of potentially pathogenic bacteria in game species is directly relevant for game meat safety. This study therefore investigated the occurrence and genomic characteristics of staphylococci, with a focus on methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), in huntable wildlife species and sympatric livestock in northern Germany.

The study was conducted at three sites in livestock-dense regions of northern Germany, including 14 farms representing cattle, sheep, swine, and poultry systems. Livestock sampling was performed twice per farm, while game species were sampled throughout one hunting season. Wildlife sampling focused exclusively on huntable species, from which nasal swabs were collected immediately after hunting. Nasal swabs were also obtained from ruminants, and boot swabs from intensive pig and poultry systems. All isolates were further characterized using whole-genome sequencing.

A total of 140 game animals were sampled, including roe deer (n = 59), wild boar (n = 23), fallow deer (n = 21), and European hare (n = 24). Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was not detected in any game samples, although it was present in livestock and farm environments. In contrast, *Staphylococcus aureus* was commonly detected across all investigated game species. Genomic analysis revealed diverse lineages, with only limited overlap between game and livestock isolates.

The absence of MRSA in game species suggests a limited role in its circulation within the studied systems. However, the detection of diverse *S. aureus* lineages, including potentially pathogenic strains, highlights the relevance of game species both as components of the wildlife–livestock interface and as a source of food. Occasional genotype overlap indicates potential points of interaction between game and livestock, influenced by shared habitats and contact intensity. These findings underline the importance of integrating game species into One Health surveillance frameworks, particularly with regard to both pathogen ecology and game meat safety.

1.4.5 Preliminary evidence of *Cryptosporidium* spp. circulation in wild boars in Portuguese hunting areas: a brief alert study

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Cryptosporidium spp. is a widely distributed gastrointestinal pathogen in vertebrates, such as the European wild boar. With a fecal-oral pathway, furthermore, they might spread by contaminated food and water, or by direct contact. Identifying the presence of the parasite and assessing contributing factors are crucial for evaluating and managing the risk intraspecifically and zoonotically. These elements are key to determining whether a critical control point exists in the wild boar meat production chain. Related to the presence of this parasite in wild boar populations, the handling of hunted carcasses may also be a source of zoonotic transmission. This work aims to evaluate the presence of *Cryptosporidium* spp. in 10 Portuguese hunting areas in 2 different locations (North and Centre of Portugal) and to preliminarily assess the risk factors of zoonotic transmission to hunting stakeholders. *Cryptosporidium* spp. antigens were confirmed by immunochromatography test in the wild boars' fecal samples of 4 of the 10 hunting areas analyzed (1 in the North and 3 in the Southeast of Central Portugal). A qualitative assessment of potential factors contributing to the persistence of infection in this wild population, as well as zoonotic risk factors related to hygiene procedures and the handling of carcasses after hunting, was also carried out. Given these potentially risky practices, it is imperative to raise awareness and establish a surveillance network in hunting areas to mitigate the risk of zoonotic transmission of these pathogenic agents to hunting stakeholders.

Veterinarians, hunters, and consumers must adopt strict hygiene and biosecurity measures. Monitoring wild species like wild boar is vital to safeguard public health and food safety, as they can harbor zoonotic parasites, such as *Cryptosporidium* spp.

1.4.6 Epidemiological Analysis and Reflection on African Swine Fever in Wild Boar (2022–2025) and Implications for Safe Game Meat

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Introduction

The first confirmed case of African swine fever (ASF) in domestic pigs was recorded on 07 January 2022, followed by detection in wild boar on 15 March 2022, which initiated intensive surveillance and control measures; a total of 13,305 domestic pigs (culled - dead) were safely disposed of between 2022 and 2024. After widespread outbreaks in 2022–2023, the number of cases declined significantly, with only sporadic occurrences in 2024 and no reported outbreaks in domestic pigs in 2025, indicating a substantial reduction in epidemiological pressure. Although ASF is not a zoonosis, its persistence in wild boar as a viral reservoir poses a significant risk for reintroduction into domestic herds and has important implications for safe game meat, making continuous surveillance essential for effective disease monitoring and control.

Materials and Methods

This study is based on data obtained from active and passive ASF surveillance in wild boar populations from 2022 to 2025. A total of 10717 samples were analyzed, of which 362 were positive through active surveillance and 178 through passive surveillance. Descriptive statistical methods were used to assess temporal trends and their implications for safe game meat production.

Results

In wild boar populations, ASF positivity showed an increasing trend from 2022 to 2024. In 2022, 36 positive cases were detected, corresponding to a prevalence of 1.24% (36/2,904 samples), including 29 cases from active surveillance (1.00%) and 7 from passive surveillance (46.67%).

In 2023, the number of positive cases increased to 163, with an overall prevalence of 3.93% (163/4,150 samples), including 127 cases from active surveillance (3.09%) and 36 from passive surveillance (94.74%).

The peak was recorded in 2024, with 331 positive cases and an overall prevalence of 10.77% (331/3,075 samples), comprising 206 cases from active surveillance (7.00%) and 125 from passive surveillance (95.42%).

In 2025, 54 positive cases were recorded, corresponding to a prevalence of 3.67% (54/1,472 samples), including 44 cases from active surveillance (3.02%) and 10 from passive surveillance (66.67%). Although a decrease in absolute numbers was observed compared to previous years, the total number of tested samples in 2025 (1,457) was considerably lower than in 2023 (4,112) and 2024 (2,944), limiting direct comparability of the results across years.

Discussion

The apparent decrease in ASF-positive cases in 2025 cannot be interpreted as a true reduction in viral circulation due to reduced sampling intensity and possible population changes in wild boar.

Despite the absence of ASF outbreaks in domestic pigs in 2025, the continued circulation of the virus in wild boar maintains a persistent epidemiological risk. Wild

populations act as a reservoir, enabling long-term environmental persistence and potential reintroduction into domestic herds.

From a safe game meat perspective, strict biosecurity measures are required throughout hunting, transport, storage, and processing. Although ASF is not zoonotic, contaminated meat products remain an important transmission pathway and a risk for the livestock sector.

Conclusion

The epidemiological data demonstrate variability in ASF occurrence in wild boar populations, emphasizing that trend interpretation must consider surveillance intensity and sampling coverage. ASF epidemiology between 2022 and 2025 shows contrasting trends, with a clear decline in domestic pigs and continued circulation in wild boar populations. While no ASF outbreaks in domestic pigs were reported by 2025, wildlife reservoirs remain a key challenge.

Ensuring safe game meat requires an integrated approach involving continuous and representative surveillance, strengthened biosecurity practices, and education of all stakeholders within the production chain. Only through such coordinated efforts can the risk of disease spread be minimized and the safe utilization of game meat be ensured.

2 Abstracts – Poster Presentations

2.1 Hunting and Processing

2.1.1 Ostrich meat as an alternative red meat source: Physicochemical and nutritional characteristics

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The aim of this study was to investigate the physicochemical characteristics and nutritional quality of ostrich meat through the evaluation of pH, water-holding capacity, proximate composition, mineral content and fatty acid profile of three muscles (*m. iliofibularis*, *m. gastrocnemius* and *m. iliotibialis*) from South African Black ostriches (*Struthio camelus* var. *domesticus*) slaughtered at 13–14 months of age.

Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed among muscles in pH measured 1.5 h post mortem, water-holding capacity and cooking loss during thermal processing. No significant differences were found among muscles in moisture, protein, fat, ash content or energy value. Iron content was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in *m. iliotibialis* (2.99 mg/100 g) than in *m. iliofibularis* (2.42 mg/100 g) and *m. gastrocnemius* (2.34 mg/100 g). No significant differences were found in phosphorus (186–201 mg/100 g), calcium (6.63–6.82 mg/100 g) or sodium (34.39–35.93 mg/100 g) contents among muscles. Lead (0.04–0.06 mg/kg) and cadmium (0.003–0.004 mg/kg) concentrations were far below the maximum permissible levels (0.1 and 0.05 mg/kg, respectively).

The predominant fatty acids in the muscles were oleic acid (C18:1n-9c), followed by palmitic (C16:0), linoleic (C18:2n-6c), palmitoleic (C16:1), arachidonic (C20:4n-6) and stearic acid (C18:0). Most other fatty acids were present in low amounts (<1%). Significant differences were found among muscles in the content of most fatty acids. Overall, *m. iliofibularis* exhibited the most favorable fatty acid profile.

The findings indicate that ostrich meat has desirable nutritional and safety characteristics, supporting its potential as a sustainable alternative to conventional red meat.

Keywords: ostrich meat, meat quality, food safety, fatty acid profile, sustainable meat production.

2.1.2 Game hunting particularities in Romania in the European context

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Introduction: Hunting in Romania is regulated by a national hunting law (Law No. 407/2006 on hunting and protection of the hunting fund, which establishes the legal framework for the management of wildlife of hunting interest, the organization of hunting activities and environmental protection). In the European context, Romania combines a highly centralized hunting system with some of the continent's highest densities of large carnivores and a significant, though not dominant, contribution to EU game-meat production.

Aims: The aim of this study was to assess the particularities of hunting in Romania over several years, with emphasis on species structure, temporal trends, and their implications for consumer safety and sustainable management in a European context.

Materials and Methods: The research material was represented by primary data provided by Romanian General Association of Hunters. Results were interpreted in relation to published European hunting and game-meat production data.

Results: The analysis showed marked variation in the structure and volume of harvested species between years. These changes were associated mainly with the expansion of predator populations and the occurrence of infectious diseases, particularly in wild boar. Ungulates (roe deer, wild boar, red deer) remained the dominant game, providing thousands of tons of meat annually, while small game (pheasant, certain ducks and geese, European hare) represented a minor share of the total hunting bag. When viewed against European data, Romania appears among the more important game-meat producers in the EU, yet its contribution still accounts for only a limited share of the total European output.

Conclusion: Hunting in Romania is characterized by a strong focus on ungulates, high predator pressure, and significant game-meat production, alongside strict legal regulation. Compared with other European countries, Romania's centralized hunting model, rich large-carnivore fauna and notable but moderate share in EU game-meat production underline both its importance and the need for careful, science-based management to ensure consumer safety and long-term sustainability.

Keywords: Hunting, game meat, Romania, consumer safety, sustainable environment, wildlife management, Europe.

2.1.3 Türkiye – Antalya – Düzlerçamı Wildlife Conservation Areas

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In Türkiye, the responsibilities of the Game and Wildlife Branch Directorate are carried out in accordance with the provisions outlined in the Land Hunting Law No. 4915, enacted on July 1, 2003. The Düzlerçamı Wildlife Conservation Area is located within Antalya Province. It was officially designated as a Wildlife Conservation Area by a Council of Ministers decision on October 16, 2005. The area designated covers 27,023 hectares. The geographical coordinates of Düzlerçamı (Antalya) are Latitude 37.025951 and Longitude 30.492170, with an average elevation of 458 meters. According to 2024 data for Türkiye, there are 85 Wildlife Development Areas encompassing a total of 169,873 hectares. The principal target species designated for the establishment of the Düzlerçamı Wildlife Conservation Areas are the fallow deer (*Dama dama*) and the mountain goat (*Capra aegagrus*). Extensive field studies, observations, and literature reviews indicate that the region is abundant in faunal elements, including mammals, birds, reptiles, fish, salamanders, and frogs, in addition to the aforementioned species. Notably, the Fallow Deer, acknowledged as the target species, is endemic to the Düzlerçamı region in Anatolia, its native habitat, with no other extant populations remaining elsewhere in Anatolia. This highlights the importance of the area. The region's diverse topography—comprising deep canyons, extensive plateaus, small hills, and rising mountains, as well as rugged, steep cliffs and rocky terrain—supports a rich diversity of flora and fauna. At lower altitudes, vegetation primarily consists of red pine and maquis. The visitor centre of Termessos National Park is situated within the Düzlerçamı Wildlife Conservation Area in Antalya. The information centre provides materials emphasizing the region's diverse flora and fauna. Educational programs are systematically arranged for student groups to enhance their understanding of the local wildlife. Recreational activities available in and around the area include botanical research, wildlife observation (such as fallow deer and mountain goats), bird-watching excursions, trekking, caving, mountain biking, camping, canyoning, and equestrian pursuits. The General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks establishes an annual hunting quota for wild goats in the region, based on population status. Within this framework, hunting tourism is facilitated by permitting both local and international hunters to hunt wild goats.

2.1.4 Preliminary Results from a European Survey on Hunting and Game Meat in Veterinary Students

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Veterinarians play a central role in wildlife health surveillance and game meat safety, making veterinary students' views on hunting and game related issues highly relevant for education and training.

Within the framework of the COST Action SafeGameMeat a cross-sectional, anonymous online survey was conducted among students enrolled in Veterinary Medicine programmes at European universities. Using a revised questionnaire, the survey aimed to characterise veterinary students' demographic profiles and their views of hunting and game-related topics. Preliminary results are herewith presented.

A total of 1,545 students from 48 universities across 29 European countries completed the survey. The median age was 24 years (range 19–69); 80% identified as female, 18% as male, and 2% preferred not to disclose. Overall, 42% were enrolled in the early years (1st–3rd) and 58% in the later years (4th–6th) of veterinary training. Only 6% reported being hunters themselves, while 35% had hunters among family members or friends. Overall, 22% reported not consuming meat, whereas 64% reported consuming game meat. Most students (71%) associate this consumption with Meat from animals in their natural habitat not raised in captivity. Hunting was primarily associated with animal population control (71%). The role of veterinary medicine in relation to game animals was most often linked to Protection of public health and to Research in epidemiology and emerging diseases (both 71%).

A substantial proportion of the respondents were unsure whether their veterinary curriculum adequately addressed hunting and game meat topics (42%), and 33% considered this training insufficient. Only 24% perceived work with game animals as an attractive career option, while attitudes towards hunting were generally balanced, with 27% reporting a neutral stance.

This first large-scale European survey highlights key perceptions and educational gaps among veterinary students regarding hunting and game-related issues.

2.1.5 Hunting Hygiene Training Systems in the European Union – A Scored SWOT assessment

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¹ Safe Game SWOT-working group, Cilento, Napoli, January 2026

Hunting hygiene training is a key component of the One Health approach, connecting wildlife management, and the protection of public and animal health across Europe. Through safe handling of game meat and early detection of wildlife diseases, such training contributes to the prevention of zoonotic risks at the human–animal–environment interface.

This study assessed hunting hygiene training systems using a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) framework. A multi-criterion scoring matrix was applied to each SWOT quadrant across weighted dimensions, with prioritization based on 1–5 Likert-scale scores. Final scores were calculated multiplicatively to highlight factors consistently performing well across all criteria.

The highest-scoring strengths (80/125) reflected effective One Health integration, including comprehensive hunt-to-slaughter competence, strong veterinarian–hunter collaboration, and early disease detection capacities supporting hazard surveillance. In contrast, critical weaknesses predominated. The lack of harmonized training standards across EU Member States and variability in legislative frameworks received the maximum score (125/125), while the absence of mandatory practical training components and unclear legal responsibilities further undermined system coherence (100/125). Key opportunities (80/125) included cross-border professional networking, shared digital training resources, and validated certification renewal systems. Major threats identified were inadequate online training delivery, failure to meet defined learning objectives, unaddressed hunter competence gaps, and shortcomings in legislative implementation (20/25). Strengthening EU-level standardization, mandatory practical training, and certification governance is essential to improve One Health outcomes and safeguard public, animal, and ecosystem health.

2.1.6 Effects of meat ageing techniques on the quality of common eland (*Taurotragus oryx*) meat.

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Limited scientific information is available on the processing of game meat to optimise eating quality, which is particularly true for antelope species. The common eland antelope (*Taurotragus oryx*) has demonstrated potential for meat production both in its place of origin southern Africa and in European countries such as the Czech Republic; however, its meat tenderness necessitates ageing. Furthermore, whilst its high polyunsaturated fatty acid content is beneficial for human health, it may increase susceptibility to oxidation and microbial spoilage during ageing. Due to the low-fat content of eland meat, high moisture losses are experienced under dry ageing, whilst wet ageing develops sour aromas and flavours. This study assessed the effects of wet (W), dry (D), and semipermeable bag (SB) ageing on physicochemical, sensory, and microbiological attributes of eland meat. Six adult females were slaughtered under controlled conditions at the CZU Common Eland Research Facilities and processed at the experimental abattoir of the Institute of Animal Sciences Prague. At 24 hours post-mortem, their longissimus lumborum muscles were divided and assigned to W, D, or SB ageing for 14 or 28 days under controlled conditions in an ageing chamber. All total bacterial counts were below thresholds for the treatments assessed. Lactic acid bacteria growth decreased when D ageing was utilised, whilst mold & yeast growth increased, compared to other ageing treatments. However, D ageing eland meat for 28 days scored highest for overall acceptance, due to higher beef aroma and roasted flavour scores, and lower abnormal odour scores. Ageing reduced shear force across all treatments, within 14 days; however, SB ageing decreased moisture losses compared to D and showed intermediary sensory scores, balancing ageing losses and flavour development whilst providing a safe product for consumers.

2.1.7 Meat inspection of wild game in Finland

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Data on meat inspection results of wild game is scarce. In Finland, number of meat inspections, total condemnations and partial condemnations are collected and published by Finnish Food Authority (FFA). The data is collected from moose (*Alces alces*), other cervids, bear (*Ursus arctos*), wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) and others. Therefore, species specific data is available only for moose, bear and wild boar and data on other species is aggregated. The hunting bag statistics are collected and published by National Resources Institute Finland (Luke).

In 2020–2024, ca. 622 000 large wild game animals were hunted in Finland. 199 000 (32%) were moose and 416 000 (67%) other cervids. The most hunted cervid was white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*). In addition, ca. 5 700 wild boar and 1 100 bears were hunted.

Only a small proportion of the hunted wild game is meat inspected. Most of the meat is consumed by the hunters and their families. However, according to national rules, hunters and hunting clubs can also sell small amounts of small wild game and wild cervids, as well as small amounts of wild game meat, directly to consumers. Species susceptible to trichinella, such as wild boars and bears must be tested negative for trichinella if sold to consumers. Hunters and hunting clubs can also sell small amounts of meat from small wild game and wild cervids to local retail without meat inspection. No data is available on the quantity of carcasses and game meat sold without meat inspection.

In 2020–2024, ca. 12 300 animals were meat inspected of which 800 (7%) were moose, 10 600 (86%) other cervids, 180 (1%) bears, 7 (0.06%) wild boar and 700 (6%) other animals. 0% (wild boar) to 2.2% (bear) carcasses were totally and 0% (wild boar) to 36% (other animals) were partially condemned. The condemnation causes are not collected by the FFA. More detailed collected data would be needed to understand the considerable variation in the condemnations.

2.2 Chemical Hazards

2.2.1 Toxic Element Accumulation in Wild Game Tissues: A Food Safety Concern

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Game meat is increasingly recognized as a valuable source of animal protein due to its high nutritional value, including highly bioavailable protein, unsaturated fatty acids, and essential macro- and micronutrients, while remaining relatively low in calories. Consequently, meat from wild game species is often regarded as a component of health-promoting diets.

However, long-term monitoring studies conducted in Poland indicate elevated concentrations of toxic elements, particularly lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and mercury (Hg), in tissues of wild game animals. Exceedances of the maximum levels (MLs) established by Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/915 are frequently observed. The MLs for Pb are 0.10 mg/kg in meat and 0.50 mg/kg in edible offal, whereas for Cd they are 0.05 mg/kg in meat, 0.50 mg/kg in liver, and 1.0 mg/kg in kidneys. In addition, Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/73 established maximum residue levels (MRLs) for Hg of 0.015 mg/kg in wild game meat, 0.025 mg/kg in edible offal of wild game animals, and 0.10 mg/kg in wild boar offal.

Particular concern is associated with Pb concentrations in muscle tissue, which may reach up to 1000 mg/kg (Szkoda, Żmudzki, Nawrocka & Kmiecik, 2013). Previous studies demonstrated that such elevated concentrations are unlikely to result solely from environmental exposure. Significantly lower Pb concentrations in kidneys and livers suggest that carcass contamination primarily originates from residues of lead-based hunting ammunition. Furthermore, Pb and Cd concentrations reported in tissues of pigs and cattle within the Polish national monitoring programme are considerably lower, with exceedances occurring only sporadically.

2.2.2 Wild boar liver from Serbia as a source of OHCs and NDL-PCBs: A risk perspective

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Wild animals are generally more prone to accumulating organochlorine compounds (OHCs) and non-dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (NDL-PCBs) than farm animals, mainly due to their feeding behavior and environmental exposure. A total of 82 liver samples were analyzed by GC-MS method, revealing the presence of minimum one residue in the liver of the majority of animals (92.7%). In this study, no statistically significant differences in OHC and NDL-PCB levels were observed in the liver with respect to age, gender, or hunting location. The residue profiles in wild boar liver showed a clear predominance of certain compounds, following the order: Σ endrin > Σ dieldrin > Σ HCH > Σ NDL-PCB > Σ DDT > Σ CHL > Σ endosulfan > methoxychlor. A preliminary risk assessment was performed using the acute reference dose (ARfD) established by FAO/WHO. The results indicate that 1.2% of liver samples may pose a health risk due to elevated Σ endrin levels (health index, HI=1.31). The risk associated with NDL-PCBs appears to be more significant, as 4.9% of samples exceeded safe intake levels after a single meal (HI values up to 32.86%). The estimated dietary intake of NDL-PCBs from wild boar liver substantially exceeded background exposure levels reported by EFSA, in some cases reaching more than 150% of typical weekly intake. The elevated contaminant levels likely are related to the specific environmental conditions in Vojvodina, a region characterized by intensive agricultural production and abundant use of specific pesticides before they have been banned in the 1990s. The results of this study indicate that consumption of wild boar liver, particularly if frequent, may represent a non-negligible health risk. This is especially relevant for population groups such as hunters and their families, who are more likely to consume such products regularly. These findings highlight the importance of continued monitoring and targeted risk communication.

Key words: endrin, EDI, ARfD, MPR, HI

2.3 Biological Hazards

2.3.1 Biological agent for combating biofilm on the game meat slaughtering surfaces: Bacteriophages

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Stainless steel, rubber and plastic equipment are often used in the slaughter and processing of game animals. This equipment, which is contaminated with pathogenic microorganisms, negatively affects slaughter hygiene, endangers public health and shortens the storage time of game meat. In this context, the sanitation of the surfaces and equipment used in slaughtering is very important. However, one of the major problems to the destruction of bacteria by conventional cleaning and disinfection on these surfaces is biofilms, which are reservoirs for pathogens. Biofilm is an extracellular polysaccharide structure formed by various bacteria and acts as a matrix in which cells can be found. In this microenvironment, bacteria that adhere to cutting equipment surfaces become resistant to environmental conditions and chemicals, and become a constant source of contamination because they cannot be removed from the surfaces. In this context, bacteriophages are one of the environmentally friendly and biological approaches in the fight against biofilms in slaughtering equipment.

In this study, the effect of bacteriophages on *Escherichia coli* O157:H7, *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilms on stainless steel, rubber and plastic surfaces was investigated. The single and multiple biofilm-forming properties of the identified pathogens were first investigated in a 96-well polystyrene plate. The effects of bacteriophage cocktails on biofilms were examined on polystyrene (as plastic), rubber and stainless-steel surfaces using strains whose biofilm-forming capacity was determined.

It was found that all bacterial groups analyzed in the study formed biofilms. Furthermore, in multiple bacterial environments, *S. Enteritidis*, *S. aureus* and *L. monocytogenes* have been found to have synergistic effects with *E. faecalis* and cause increased biofilm formation. It was observed that bacteriophage cocktails in biofilm groups formed by bacteria in polystyrene plates reduced the number of bacteria in the biofilm at a level of 1.90 to 5.82 log CFU/mL. Similarly, bacteriophage cocktails were found to reduce the number of bacteria in the biofilm by 2.70 to 5.48 log CFU/mL on stainless steel and rubber surfaces. As a result, it was revealed that the phage cocktails used in this study were effective on biofilms formed on stainless steel, rubber and plastic surfaces, which are the materials of the equipment used in the slaughter of game meats, and there was no significant difference between this effect depending on the material.

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2.3.2 Legal Framework for Game and Wildlife-Derived Products in Türkiye

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The initial regulation in Türkiye, titled "Regulation on the Possession, Production, and Trade of Game and Wild Animals and Products Derived Therefrom, " was published in the Official Gazette on June 16, 2005 (Official Gazette No. 25847 dated 16/06/2005). Since that time, Türkiye has implemented comprehensive regulations governing the possession, production, and trade of products derived from game and wild animals, addressing pertinent issues within their scope.

The establishment of specialised production facilities pertains to applications for the establishment and granting of permits for small, medium, and large-scale facilities that produce game and wild animals. This includes ensuring hygienic conditions, conducting health screenings, and implementing disease control measures within production facilities. Activities also encompass keeping live game and wild animals as hobbies, as well as possessing and collecting their products. Furthermore, this involves the collection and application of products derived from game and wild animals, applications to museums to exhibit such products, and the sale of furs and skins. The transportation of live game and wild animals and their products, together with the import and export of species and their derivatives, are also included within this framework.

Trade in hunted species (Article 64). The purchase and sale of meat from species whose hunting is permitted, except for wild boar, are prohibited. However, the meat of game animals hunted within the scope of hunting tourism is evaluated in accordance with the principles of the Regulation on Procedures and Principles Regarding Hunting by Domestic and Foreign Hunters within the Scope of Hunting Tourism, published in the Official Gazette dated 8/1/2005 and numbered 25694.

In accordance with Article 65 regarding the trade in wild boar meat, any individual or entity intending to engage in the commerce of meat derived from hunted wild boars must secure a designated permit from the Ministry. This regulation supplements their existing licenses for commercial operations, which are essential for trade and export. It is crucial that both natural and legal persons manage hunted wild boars solely with appropriate authorisation and adhere strictly to regulations that prohibit dismembering or modifying carcasses into meat.

This regulation delineates the legal framework for the conservation and sustainable utilisation of game and wild animals, as well as the production, possession, and commerce of derivatives thereof. It institutes an extensive oversight and control system to safeguard food safety and public health through measures such as restrictions on the trade in game meat, the requirement for a specialised permit for wild boar meat, and the obligation to submit veterinary health certificates and transportation permits.

2.3.3 Beaver (*Castor fiber* L.) as source of new danger for trophic chain

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Despite beavers are increasingly recognized as "ecosystem engineers" that, while enhancing biodiversity in many contexts, can also introduce new dangers and complexities to trophic chains. Since beavers are herbivores, their infection is likely linked to consumption of plants contaminated by animals. Although rare, cases of *Trichinella* infection in beavers have been confirmed in the Baltic region, with studies in Latvia detecting *T. britovi* (0.5% prevalence). A case of *T. spiralis* in beaver meat has also been reported in Poland and Lithuania (2026, April, Vilnius Region).

We do not think that it could be case of beaver necrophagy (carrion feeding) during periods of high environmental stress or protein deficiency, or to territorial fights with predators like wolves. However, such cases are possible as displacement behaviour in beaver when it could consume some carrion as additional source of protein.

As beaver meat becomes a popular game delicacy in Lithuania, consumption of raw or undercooked meat poses a risk. The State Food and Veterinary Service (VMVT) highlights that, like wild boars, beaver meat should be tested for *Trichinella*.

In many contexts, can also introduce new dangers and complexities to trophic chains, particularly when introduced outside their native range or when their populations surge in altered landscapes. Their impact is mostly positive in native ecosystems, but they can act as a catalyst for ecosystem degradation where they act as invasive species.

2.3.4 Prevalence and molecular insights into *Alaria alata* mesocercariae infecting selected sylvatic hosts in Poland over a seven-year survey

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Background: *Alaria alata* is a zoonotic trematode widely distributed in European wildlife, with wild mammals serving as important paratenic hosts in its life cycle. The present study aimed to assess the prevalence and genetic diversity of *A. alata* mesocercariae in selected sylvatic hosts in Poland over a long-term surveillance period.

Methods: Muscle and adipose tissue samples were collected from wildlife originating from all 16 voivodeships of Poland. In total, 3,250 wild boars sampled between 2018 and 2025 were examined, together with 247 raccoon dogs and 106 badgers hunted during 2024–2025. Additionally, 19 raccoons were included in the survey in 2025. All samples were analyzed using the *Alaria* mesocercariae migration technique (AMT). Species identification was performed by morphological examination followed by amplification and sequence analysis of partial fragments of the nuclear 18S rRNA gene and the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene.

Results: *Alaria alata* mesocercariae were detected in 351 of 3,250 wild boars (10.8%), 81 of 247 raccoon dogs (32.8%), 22 of 106 badgers (20.8%), and 2 of 19 raccoons (10.5%). Morphological characteristics of all recovered larvae were consistent with *A. alata*. PCR amplification of the 18S rRNA (232 bp) and COI (450 bp) gene fragments produced products of the expected sizes. Sequence comparison using BLAST, GenBank, and Geneious software confirmed species identity in all isolates. Analysis of the mitochondrial COI gene revealed 1–7 single nucleotide polymorphisms, demonstrating substantial intraspecific genetic diversity among the examined samples.

Conclusions: The results indicate that wild boars, raccoon dogs, badgers, and raccoons contribute to the maintenance of *A. alata* in the sylvatic environment in Poland. The relatively high prevalence observed in carnivorous hosts highlights their epidemiological importance in parasite transmission. The genetic variability identified among isolates expands current knowledge of *A. alata* population structure and may support future improvements in surveillance strategies and regulations concerning carcass handling when *Alaria* mesocercariae are detected.

2.3.5 Roe deer fecal enterococci: A reservoir of potential pathogenic strains

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The gut microbiota is a key component of host physiology, influencing nutrient metabolism, immune system regulation, and protection against pathogenic microorganisms. Although considerable attention has been devoted to the microbiota of domesticated animals, data on wild ungulates remain limited. This study focuses on enterococci isolated from fecal samples of wild roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*) in eastern Slovakia with the aim of characterizing their potential as reservoirs of traits associated with virulence, with particular emphasis on virulence factor genes.

A total of 20 fecal samples were collected at the Zádiel site (Slovakia) and processed using standardized microbiological procedures in accordance with ISO protocols. Samples were cultured on selective media, including M-*Enterococcus* agar, and species identification was performed using MALDI-TOF MS. The presence of selected virulence-associated genes (*gelE*, *esp*, *cyl*, *efa*, *agg*, *hyl*, IS16, *ccf*, *cpd*) was subsequently determined by PCR analysis.

In total, 25 enterococcal isolates were identified and classified into three species: *Enterococcus faecalis* (n = 9), *Enterococcus mundtii* (n = 15), and *Enterococcus casseliflavus* (n = 1). Among the analyzed genes, *esp* was the most prevalent, detected in 64% of strains, predominantly within *E. mundtii* species (14/15). The *ccf* and *hyl* genes were identified in 52% of strains, while *gelE* and *cpd* were present in 44%. Notably, the *cyl* gene, commonly associated with increased pathogenicity, was not detected in any strain. The findings indicate that enterococci from wild roe deer harbor multiple virulence-associated determinants, particularly *esp*, *gelE*, *hyl*, and IS16. Moreover, *E. faecalis* strains exhibited more complex virulence gene profile, resembling those typically described in clinically relevant strains. These results support the hypothesis that free-living wild animals may act as a natural reservoir of enterococci with pathogenic potential, even in the absence of direct antibiotic selection pressure. From a One Health perspective, continuous monitoring of microbial communities in wild animals is essential, as they may contribute to the environmental circulation of opportunistic pathogens.

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2.3.6 Biological Hazards in the Game Meat Chain: Implications for Food Safety and Public Health

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Viral hepatitis E represents their occurrence, risks to consumers, and outlining knowledge gaps and needs for future research or surveillance.

The game meat industry is a one-of-a-kind and increasing portion of the world's food systems. It has changeable weather patterns, harvesting methods that are spread out, and less government supervision than traditional animal husbandry. These things make biological risks more likely, which could put the health of the population and the safety of food at risk. Game animals can contain a multitude of diseases that can spread to humans, such as bacteria like *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli* (particularly strains that make shiga toxin), and *Listeria monocytogenes*, as well as parasites like *Trichinella* spp., *Toxoplasma gondii*, and other helminths. Also, game meat that isn't cooked properly or isn't prepared well could spread several viral infections.

Contamination can happen at several important points in the game meat supply chain, such as hunting, field dressing, evisceration, shipping, processing, and storage. Not following proper hygiene standards, not handling things correctly, not cooling carcasses quickly enough, and being among environmental toxins all make it far more likely that microbes will grow and spread. Rural areas may not have sanitary facilities, which makes it harder to follow basic food safety rules. This is different from regulated slaughterhouse surroundings.

If there aren't any or they aren't always followed, veterinary inspection methods in some areas make it more likely that tainted or sick corpses will get into the food supply. Wildlife ecology, seasonal changes, and differences between regions all affect how common diseases are and how they spread. Foodborne illness is more likely to happen when people do things like eat traditional foods and don't prepare food properly.

To effectively reduce risk, solutions must take into account the unique features of game meat production and be based on a "farm-to-fork" approach. Important procedures are to provide specialized education and training for hunters and processors, follow proper cleanliness and handling standards, chill the meat right after it is harvested, and use hazard analysis and critical control point (HACCP) systems when they are needed. To lower biological risks, it is important to improve monitoring programs, make regulatory frameworks more effective, and raise consumer awareness. For the sake of public health and the long-term utilization of animal resources, it is important to make the game meat supply chain safer.

Keywords: Game meat; Biological hazards; Food safety; Zoonotic pathogens; Public health

2.3.7 Chemical composition and microbiological quality of wild game meat intended for household consumption

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Wild game meat is increasingly valued as an alternative source of animal protein due to its nutritional properties and consumer preference for more natural foods. However, meat obtained through hunting is often consumed within hunters' households without official postmortem veterinary inspection, which may increase food safety concerns related to carcass handling, field dressing, and transport conditions.

This study aimed to evaluate the chemical composition and microbiological quality of wild game meat intended for household consumption. Between November 2024 and May 2025, 50 meat samples were collected from deer, roe deer, wild boar, and bear harvested in three hunting areas located in Maramureş and Bistriţa counties, Romania. Samples were analyzed for moisture, protein, fat, and collagen content using FoodScan technology. Microbiological analyses included aerobic plate count, Enterobacteriaceae, and *Escherichia coli*, determined using standardized methods.

The results showed that game meat was characterized by low fat content and relatively high protein levels compared with conventional meat from farmed animals. Bear meat showed the highest protein and fat contents, whereas deer meat presented the lowest fat values. Roe deer meat had the lowest protein content among the species analyzed. Microbiological examination revealed the presence of Enterobacteriaceae and *E. coli* in some samples, indicating contamination associated with inadequate hygiene during skinning, evisceration, handling, or transport. Although microbial counts were higher than those commonly reported for meat from slaughtered domestic animals, these findings reflect the specific conditions under which wild game is harvested and processed.

Wild game meat represents a valuable nutritional resource with favorable compositional characteristics; however, improved hygiene practices during field dressing, carcass handling, chilling, and transport are essential to enhance its microbiological safety for consumers.

2.3.8 An atypical case of macroscopic sarcocystosis in a wild boar intended for human consumption in Italy

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Sarcocystis spp. are protozoan parasites with a worldwide distribution, infecting a wide range of hosts involved in a predator–prey life cycle. Humans can become infected by consuming raw or undercooked beef or pork, thereby developing intestinal sarcocystosis.

Among wild game, wild boars act as intermediate hosts of the zoonotic *Sarcocystis suis/hominis* and the canid-transmitted *Sarcocystis miescheriana*, usually developing subclinical infections. Gross lesions associated with sarcocystosis are extremely rare and have only occasionally been reported. Herein, we describe a case of macroscopic sarcocystosis detected in a 5-year-old male wild boar (150 kg) hunted in the province of Messina (Sicily, Italy).

During post-mortem inspection, multiple whitish, elongated cyst-like lesions resembling rice grains were observed within various skeletal muscles. Histopathological examination revealed granulomatous foci with central necrosis/mineralization, peripheral mononuclear-to-eosinophilic infiltrates, and frequent perilesional intact sarcocysts. Molecular analyses targeting the mitochondrial *cox1* gene confirmed the presence of *S. miescheriana* DNA.

To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first report of macroscopic sarcocystosis in wild boar in Italy and the second case worldwide associated with grossly visible lesions. The infection resulted in generalized muscular involvement and raised concerns regarding carcass fitness for human consumption. Although *S. miescheriana* is not zoonotic, the presence of macroscopic lesions requires carcass condemnation according to current European regulations, highlighting potential economic implications.

This report underlines the importance of careful inspection of game meat and contributes to the limited knowledge on the pathological manifestations of sarcocystosis in wild boar. Further studies are needed to clarify the epidemiology and clinical relevance of these unusual findings.

2.3.9 Effect of disinfectant exposure time on biofilm-associated *Salmonella enterica*: comparison of Desprej and Virusolve+

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Salmonella enterica is an important foodborne pathogen, and cells embedded within biofilms exhibit markedly greater resistance to disinfectants than their planktonic counterparts. This significantly complicates effective sanitation and contamination control in industrial environments, including meat-processing facilities, where variable hygiene conditions may favor microbial persistence.

Desprej is a disinfectant based on quaternary ammonium compounds, often combined with alcohols, acting mainly by disrupting microbial cell membranes. Virusolve+ contains hydrogen peroxide and quaternary ammonium compounds, combining membrane disruption with oxidative action, which enhances its effectiveness against biofilms and resistant microorganisms. These disinfectants are approved for use in the food industry, provided they comply with relevant regulations and are applied according to the manufacturer's instructions. They can be applied to non-porous surfaces such as equipment, worktops, and cold storage areas, as well as in niches prone to biofilm formation. Their use in routine sanitation may help limit the persistence and spread of *Salmonella* spp. The aim of this study was to assess the impact of Desprej and Virusolve+ on the growth of *Salmonella enterica*, including the reference strain *S. Typhimurium* ATCC 14028, and animal-derived isolates (*S. Senftenberg* 133 and 134). The study evaluated bacterial growth in biofilm form and further determined the effectiveness of Virusolve against Desprej-tolerant *Salmonella* variants (cross-resistance).

The study was conducted using the biofilm-oriented antiseptics test (BOAT) described by Junka et al. (2013), a colorimetric method based on tetrazolium chloride, in which bacterial biofilms were exposed to disinfectants for defined contact times (1 and 20 min). Quantitative analysis was performed by plating and calculating colony-forming units (CFU) to assess bacterial survival. The results indicate that the wild-type *S. Typhimurium* ATCC 14028 strain exhibited growth at Virusolve+ concentrations of 0.2% and lower after both 1 and 20 min of exposure. In contrast, the Desprej-tolerant variant of this strain was able to grow at a higher concentration of 6% after 1 min of exposure (no growth observed after 20 min). The wild-type *S. Senftenberg* 133 strain showed growth at a concentration of 3% after 1 minute of exposure, whereas its tolerant variant was able to grow at 6% after 1 minute. The wild-type *S. Senftenberg* 134 strain showed growth at 4% after both 1 and 20 minutes of exposure, but its Desprej-tolerant variant was able to grow at 6% after 1 minute and 5% after 20 minutes.

In conclusion, Desprej-tolerant variants of *Salmonella enterica* in biofilms exhibit increased tolerance to Virusolve+, particularly after short exposure (1 min). Prolonged exposure (20 min) reduced or eliminated bacterial survival in the case of *S. Typhimurium*, indicating that contact time remains an important factor for effective disinfection. The results indicate partial cross-tolerance rather than full cross-resistance, as Desprej-tolerant variants showed increased survival at higher Virusolve+ concentrations, but remained susceptible after prolonged exposure.

2.3.10 *Trichinella* spp. in Poland: Wild boar population insights

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Introduction

Trichinella spp. are zoonotic nematodes posed a risk of human infection by ingestion of meat containing live larvae of these parasites. In the past in Poland pork meat was the main source of infection in human, however during last two decades the risk of getting trichinellosis for consumers is connected more with consuming of wild boar meat.

Purpose

The aim of the analyses was to update data on the spread of *Trichinella* spp. in Poland.

Methods

The analyses included data on the number of wild boars shot in six hunting seasons (2015-2020), the number of wild boars infected with *Trichinella*, the population size of selected carnivores (foxes, raccoon dogs and European badgers) as well as the land cover (sites near human buildings and crops, forests and water bodies). The analyses were carried out at two levels: the national level (including data from 310 counties) and the regional level covering the area of north-western Poland (including data from 115 counties), where the higher intensity of *Trichinella* infections in wild boars was clearly visible.

Results

Wild boars' infection with *Trichinella* was significantly dependent on the settlements and forests percentage but the relations were different. The number of wild boars infected increased with the share of forests and decreased with the share of the settlements. It was found that the number of infected wild boars is probably related to the population of raccoon dogs - a *Trichinella* vector. The above data indicate that in north-western Poland trichinellosis is endemic. Statistical analyses have shown that there is a correlation between the number of wild boars infected with *Trichinella* in this area and the size of the raccoon dogs' population inhabiting the area. The analysis also showed that there are endemic areas in two Voivodeships, where the percentage of wild boars infected with trichinellosis was as high as in north-western Poland.

Significance

The statistical significance of correlation between number of raccoon dogs' population and number of infected wild boars indicate a necessity of monitoring *Trichinella* spp. in this important vector to control the further transmission of the parasite in sylvatic environment.

2.3.11 Susceptibility of fecal enterococci from European brown hares to postbiotic substances produced by lactococci

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In recent years, the European brown hare (*Lepus europaeus* Pallas 1778) has been observed to decline in occurrence. However, the European brown hare remains economically valuable as an important game species. To date, information on the individual microbiota of this game animal has remained limited. Hares were hunted in six districts of south-western Slovakia during the winter season, approved in accordance with the laws of the Slovak Republic for hunting and the Institutional Ethic Committee. The samples were kindly supplied by Ľubica Chrastinová (National Agricultural and Food Centre in Nitra-Lužianky, Slovakia). Enterococci belong to the phylum Bacillota (Firmicutes), which dominates the European brown hare microbiota. They can carry virulence factor genes; so, they can be harmful to the health of the hare, and as a game animal, also to consumers' health. In this study, *Enterococcus faecium* (Tr/1a, Tr11/b, Zih/8b, Zih/2b) and *E. faecalis* (Zih/2a) were identified using MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry and PCR with appropriate primers. They were tested for the virulence factor genes *esp*, *agg*, and *gelE*. The strains lacked of tested virulence factor genes and were susceptible to antibiotics and to three postbiotic substances produced by the strains of *Lactococcus lactis* MK2/8, MK1/3, and MK2/2 (characterized in our laboratory), deposited in GenBank under access numbers PQ158272 for MK2/8, and ON114093 for MK1/3. MK2/2 is not in GenBank. These proteinaceous antimicrobial active substances, non-purified to homogeneity, are called postbiotic substances (PS). Enterococci were more susceptible to PS/MK2/8 than to PS/MK1/3. However, *E. faecalis* EFZih/2b was the most susceptible to PS/MK2/2 out of all tested strains, with the highest value of arbitrary units (12,800 AU/ml) as the activity of PS is expressed. The susceptibility of the other strains was inhibited by used PS in the range from 400 to 6,400 AU/ml. Although the preliminary results show PS as a new tool to prevent/inhibit potential contaminant bacteria in game animals, protecting their health, followed by consumers' health.

The study was supported by the COST Action Safety in the Game Meat (SafeGameMeat, CA22166) and VEGA no. 2/0009/25.

2.3.12 Sampling methods for the detection of zoonotic pathogens in game meat – a literature review

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The consumption of game meat is increasing as a perceived natural alternative to livestock products. However, its “natural” origin also poses risks related to zoonotic pathogens at the human–animal–environment interface. While surveillance of livestock products is regulated through standardized sampling and microbiological criteria (EU 2073/2005), monitoring approaches for game meat remain less harmonized, limiting comparability and weakening the One Health framework.

This study systematically looked into international peer-reviewed publications to evaluate sampling methodologies for zoonotic pathogens in game meat and to identify critical gaps in hygiene, documentation, and handling. A total of 42 English-language studies (2000–2026) were retrieved from Web of Science, focusing on free-living wild game intended for human consumption. Extracted parameters included pathogen, host species, geographic origin, sampling conditions, hygiene measures, time intervals between killing and sampling, and transport conditions.

Wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) was the predominant species (81%), with Hepatitis E virus and *Toxoplasma gondii* most frequently investigated (18.2% each). Overall, reporting was frequently incomplete, particularly regarding sampling conditions, time to sampling, transport, and personnel training. Documentation of hygiene practices and time–temperature conditions was also limited.

To improve data reliability, key recommendations include standardized protocols, mandatory training of sampling personnel, and comprehensive documentation of sampling and transport conditions. The current lack of harmonized sampling and reporting limits comparability between studies and constrains robust cross-border risk assessment. Implementing these measures would strengthen surveillance and support the safe and sustainable use of game meat.

2.3.13 *Alaria alata* mesocercariae in wild boar meat – risk to public health

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Alaria alata is a trematode whose true hosts are foxes and other canid species. The adult flukes live in the intestine of the definitive hosts. In addition to intermediate hosts (pond snails and frogs), paratenic hosts (birds, snakes, pigs) that feed on frogs are also important in the life cycle of the parasite. The preferred sites of mesocercariae of *A. alata* are distributed heterogeneously throughout the body of the paratenic host. Unlike *Trichinella* larvae, which are found in the most active muscles (crura of the diaphragm, tongue). So far, mesocercariae in meat have been determined by the method of artificial digestion and compression, and a method of mesocercariae migration has also been developed. This method detects infected pigs that gave a false negative result for *Alaria* when searching for trichinella in meat using the digestion method. *Trichinella* larvae and *Alaria* mesocercariae differ in their resistance and ability to maintain vitality in relation to thermal processing and storage regimes. The study of the viability of mesocercariae in meat products prepared in a traditional way showed that only fresh products contain live mesocercariae and can be a source of infection for humans. Data on the infection of wild and domestic pigs with metacercariae of *A. alata* in Europe have recently been increasing. The zoonotic potential of alariasis with serious consequences for patients has been documented after the consumption of insufficiently thermally processed frog legs and pig meat. Human disease often occurs in the form of mild infections that may remain unrecognized. The possibility of human infection depends primarily on the prevalence of *A. alata* in the wild and pasture-raised pig population, and then on the method of preparation of the meat for consumption. Based on previous research in Serbia, its prevalence is around 3% of examined wild boars.

2.3.14 Fecal staphylococci from pheasants and their treatment using lantibiotic bacteriocin-gallidermin

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The common pheasant is a well-known gamebird and one of the most hunted birds worldwide. Pheasant meat is highly nutritious and considered a culinary delicacy. Although information on staphylococcal species detected in pheasants is limited, the primary concern has focused on methicillin-resistant staphylococci (MRS) as potential causative agents in pheasant husbandry. Given that pheasant meat is used as food, it can pose a health risk to consumers. Twelve biogenic amine-producing fecal staphylococcal strain species were tested. They were isolated from 60 pheasants. Handling and care were provided with acceptance of the Slovak Veterinary and Food Administration and the breeders. The following staphylococcal species strains were tested: *Staphylococcus lentus* (SL31, SL32), *S. succinus* (SU52, SU61, SU62, SU63, SU64, and SU65), *S. hominis* (SHo13, SHo54), *S. hyicus* SHy53, and *S. cohnii* SCo61. They were identified using the MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. Staphylococci were tested for the production of biogenic amines, including tryptamine (TRYP), phenylethylamine (PEA), putrescine (PUT), cadaverine (CAD), histamine (HIS), tyramine (TYM), spermine (SPN), and spermidine (SPD) in co-operation with colleagues Leona Buňková and Pavel Pleva of Tomáš Baťa University in Zlín, Faculty of Technology, Department of Environmental Protection Engineering (Czech Republic). In vitro, staphylococcal susceptibility to gallidermin was tested by the agar spot test. Gallidermin belongs to the lantibiotic bacteriocins. Pure gallidermin (Enzo Life Sciences Corporation USA, MW2069.4) was used for testing (0.5 mg/mL, 2 µL dose as determined in previous testing). The strain SL32 produced the highest amount of TYM (1150.42 ± 72.04 mg/L), followed by *S. succinus* SU52 (999.53 ± 37.58 mg/L) and SCo61 (918.32 ± 37.58 mg/L). The average TYM value was 543.80 ± 23.31 mg/L. In general, PEA was produced in medium and/or high amounts, with the highest value in SL32 (451.03 ± 35.12 mg/L). SL32 also produced the highest amount of SPD, although its production was lower than that of other BA, similar to SPMm production. However, the strains did not produce TRYP, PUT, CAD, and HIS. Moreover, their growth was inhibited by gallidermin, with an inhibitory activity of 25,600 AU/ml, except for strains SL31 and SL32, which had an inhibitory activity of 3,200 AU/ml. Although the limited number of strains tested, the results achieved are a promising indication of further use of gallidermin for veterinary purposes.

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2.3.15 Forensic reconstruction of control failure in mandatory *Trichinella* surveillance system

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A confirmed outbreak of human trichinellosis involving eight individuals was investigated in December 2020 in the Kościan district, western Poland, following the consumption of homemade cold-smoked sausage. The investigation was initiated after notification from the local sanitary authority and was conducted jointly by the Veterinary Inspection and Public Health Services under the national contingency procedures for *Trichinella* detection. Detailed epidemiological interviews demonstrated that all affected persons belonged to three related family groups and had consumed the same batch of raw sausage distributed privately by a hunter. During the initial inquiry, the producer declared roe deer as the meat source, then changed his statement, claiming that wild boar meat had been used and officially examined for *Trichinella* in an accredited veterinary laboratory. Verification of laboratory documentation excluded submission of any such sample, confirming that mandatory preconsumption examination had not been performed. To verify the conflicting declarations, retained sausage samples collected by the Local Veterinary Officer were subjected to species identification by isoelectric focusing of muscle proteins, which unequivocally confirmed wild boar as the sole meat component. Parallel parasitological examination by the magnetic stirrer digestion method revealed heavy contamination with *Trichinella* larvae at levels of 34 and 54 larvae per gram in two independent sausage samples. Subsequent multiplex PCR performed according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites protocol identified the larvae as *Trichinella spiralis*. The integrated findings demonstrated a complete breach of the official control barrier: the omission of obligatory carcass testing, false and changing declarations concerning meat origin, and the undocumented, informal distribution of a high-risk raw product among relatives and acquaintances. The case highlights that a single unexamined wild boar carcass entering household for processing may generate a multi-family foodborne outbreak despite the existence of a compulsory surveillance system. The study confirms the critical importance of combining veterinary traceback investigation, meat species authentication and laboratory confirmation in the forensic reconstruction of trichinellosis outbreaks.

2.3.16 Spatial distribution of *Trichinella* spp. in Poland: epidemiological patterns in wild boar and pigs (2016–2021)

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Trichinellosis remains a relevant foodborne zoonosis in Europe, with wildlife particularly wild boar constituting the primary reservoir. Poland, characterized by diverse climatic and biogeographical conditions, provides a suitable model for analyzing environmental determinants of *Trichinella* spp. distribution. Study aimed to assess the spatial distribution of *Trichinella* spp. in Poland in wild boar and pigs, with emphasis on climatic factors.

Data were collected between 2016 and 2021 within the National Reference Laboratory for *Trichinella* located at National Veterinary Research Institute in Puławy framework. Muscle samples from wild boars and pigs were examined using the magnetic stirrer digestion method (ISO 18743), followed by molecular identification (multiplex PCR). Spatial analysis was performed using GIS (QGIS), with cases mapped according to Polish physico-geographical subprovinces.

A total of 1,514 *Trichinella spiralis* and 304 *T. britovi* infections were detected in wild boars. *T. spiralis* predominated, with the highest density observed in the Southern Baltic Coastlands and Southern Baltic Lake Districts, indicating clear clustering in north-western Poland. *T. britovi* showed a more dispersed distribution, with notable occurrences in both northern lake districts and southern mountainous regions. Mixed infections (*T. spiralis*/*T. britovi*) were rare (n = 56), but also concentrated in northern regions. Other species (*T. pseudospiralis*, n = 9; *T. nativa*, n = 1) were sporadic.

In pigs, 105 cases were identified, predominantly *T. spiralis*, with clustering patterns similar to wild boar, suggesting environmental spillover and breaches in biosecurity.

The distribution of *Trichinella* spp. in Poland is spatially heterogeneous and strongly associated with environmental conditions, particularly humidity, water availability, and mild climatic regimes. Northern lake districts and coastal areas represent high-risk zones. The overlap of infections in wildlife and pigs highlights the continued relevance of environmental reservoirs and the need for strict biosecurity measures. GIS-based spatial analysis provides a valuable tool for risk assessment and targeted surveillance within veterinary public health systems.

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Safety in the Game Meat Chain Network

Under the leadership of the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), the European network 'Safety in the Game Meat Chain' (COST Action 22166, 2023–2027) promotes the exchange of knowledge regarding the health risks associated with game meat from hunted animals for consumers. The main aim and objective of the Action is to determine differences and similarities between European countries in terms of hunting practices, game meat processing and inspection, legislation, game meat commodity flows, trade and game meat consumption, investigating all stages of the supply chain from the wild animal to the consumer, “from forest to fork”. The growing network currently includes around 200 members from 40 countries, encompassing EU and non-EU member states.

www.safegamemeat.eu

